

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

PROGRESS REPORT FLAGSHIP PROJECT

SUMMER

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE D.4 - SUMMER

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
0.1	26/10/23	First draft	POLITO
0.5	28/10/23	RM1 description	POLITO
0.9	30/10/23	RM2-RM3-RM4 description	POLITO
1	31/10/23	Final draft	POLITO

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	From 1/10/2022 to 31/10/2023
Periodic report date and version:	31/10/2023, version 1

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

Contents

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile	1
<i>Version history</i>	1
Glossary	3
1. EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS	4
1.1 OBJECTIVES.....	4
1.2 WORK CARRIED OUT PER RM IN THE REPORTING PERIOD	6
1.2.1 Research Module 1	6
1.2.2 Research Module 2	11
1.2.3 Research Module 3	23
1.2.2 Research Module 4	27
2. IMPACT	30
3. INDUSTRY PARTICIPATION AND INNOVATIONS (prototypes, clinical trials, Testing activities etc)	31
4. OPEN SCIENCE PRACTISES AND UPDATE OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (IF APPLICABLE)	31
5. RESULTS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART	31
ANNEXES	32
A) LIST OF DELIVERABLES	32
B) LIST OF MILESTONES	33
C) LIST OF CRITICAL RISKS	33
D) PROJECT PATHWAY TO IMPACT: RESULTS	34
E) PUBLICATIONS	34
F) DATASETS.....	39
G) INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS (IPRs)	40
H) OTHER RESULTS	40
I) IMPACT in terms of TRLS, SDGs, KSOs	Errore. Il segnalibro non è definito.

Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

1. EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

The main objective of the SUMMER project is to accompany energy and water management into the digital era, showing how smart technology can boost the integrated management of water and energy systems. Digital technologies, combined with the power of 'big data' and AI-based analytics, drive unprecedented innovation in how energy and water utilities and companies manage these vital resources. To make the north-western Italy productive ecosystem ready to face this challenge, the project is developed around four research modules (RMs): (i) Monitoring and forecasting water resources and energy productivity at the watershed scale; (ii) Integrated management of energy production and use; (iii) Risk-resilient Energy and Water Infrastructures; (iv) Smart Energy and Water Distribution Systems.

1.1 OBJECTIVES

The long-term ambition of this flagship project is to accompany energy and water management into the digital era, showing how smart technology can boost the integrated management of water and energy systems. The project will generate collaborations between the research system, the production system and local institutions by enhancing research results, facilitating technology transfer and accelerating the digital transformation of businesses and production processes working towards an economic and environmental sustainability and social impact of the territories involved. In particular, the main objectives of the project can be summarized as follows:

Objective	RMs involved	Progress
To enhance ecosystem efficiency promoting an effective resource and energy management by monitoring and forecasting hydro-meteorological variables and assessing relevant environmental conditioning factors providing a dynamic water balance on various timescales, from some days to several months.	RM1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation and implementation of sensors for monitoring hydro-meteorological variables at Cannona, Bussoleno and Nivolet sites. • Field monitoring activities at high altitude for the quantification of SWE, both in a fixed site, and with a mobile TDR system. • Installation of an innovative sensor for the continuous quantification of flow rates in a small basin in the Olen Valley in the Monterosa2000 ski domain (Alagna, VC).
To promote the big-data revolution of monitoring and forecasting using innovative sensors, remote-sensing platforms, data-transmission tools, as well as data-storage and data-management protocols.	RM1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of a data transmission system ensuring continuous monitoring and automatic data transmission of a meteorological station in the Gran Paradiso National Park at 2600 m asl. Some antennas have been tested before finding the effective solution, now in operation.
To foster the potential of digitalization toward the efficient integration of variable renewables in the power system, by enabling grids to better match energy demand and production with renewable energy community's schema, thus	RM2 RM4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conclusion of the first draft of a co-simulation platform for the integrated management of energy and water resources conceived for design/planning, automated system optimization and decision support

accelerating the decarbonization of the electricity sector		tool.
To enhance infrastructures resilience by allowing fine-scale real-time monitoring of the existing risks, drought included, as well as by providing rapid and accurate assessment of asset condition and support decision-making and adaptation.	RM3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of a procedure for estimating the fragility curves of high-voltage pylons from avalanche impacts • Calibration of a fiber-optic system for earth embankment monitoring. • Geophysical investigations for the characterization of water basins in the Aosta Valley.
To develop 50-year global warming risk scenario maps and statistical analysis of climate and landslides/debris/avalanches data to support planning and management of infrastructures.	RM3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquisition of climate data to study the role of climate change in relation to debris flows in Aosta Valley. • Feasibility study for the implementation of a machine learning approach for generating landslide susceptibility maps.
To develop and implement innovative smart-grid solutions through smart metering and digital connectivity tools, accompanied by digital models of the networks that enable proper management of the big data generated by the sensors.	RM4 RM2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a hydropower production estimation model over the entire Orco basin hydrographic network. • Digitalization of the new aqueduct infrastructure in the Orco valley. • Development of a water resource optimization model for the Orco valley basin

1.2 WORK CARRIED OUT PER RM IN THE REPORTING PERIOD

1.2.1 Research Module 1

Research Module n.1	Start month: 1			End month: 36			
Title: Monitoring and forecasting water resources and energy productivity at the watershed scale							
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y							
RM Leader	UNITO			Prof. Stefano Ferraris			
Partners involved	POLITO	UNITO	LINKS				
Type of action:	Industrial Research						
Effort in person/months: ¹	3.04	3.40	7.68				
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):							
<p>Enhancing ecosystem efficiency and promoting valuable resources and energy management by monitoring and forecasting of hydro-meteorological variables (precipitation, evapotranspiration, wind speed, solar radiation, discharge, snow cover and snow water equivalent, carbon budget, etc.) as well as the assessment of relevant environmental conditioning factors (soil physical properties, soil moisture, soil infiltration capacity, soil permeability, rock and permafrost stability, glacier mass balance, dust and organic compounds deposition, etc.). This is even more crucial with the electricity sector becoming more decentralized with the proliferation of small and distributed energy producers connected directly to the distribution grid. Other sectors, like for example the agricultural, water supply, skiing and risk insurance industries, likewise strongly depend on innovative digital monitoring and forecasting systems. The challenge posed by these systems is especially harsh in mountain environments, typically characterized by low connectivity and accessibility conditions.</p>							
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):							
<p>Objective 1 – Innovative sensors</p> <p>Task 1 – Experiments of georadar devices to support the mass balance of Rutor Glacier, were carried out in collaboration with ARPA VdA, during May 22-24, 2023.</p> <p>In particular, ground-transported and drone-mounted georadar devices were used; the surveys carried out with 500 MHz and 900 MHz antennas were aimed at investigating on the north slope of the glacier the thickness of the snowpack, up to the most superficial layers of the firn/ice of the glacial apparatus.</p> <p>The acquisitions by drone device were essentially aimed at testing the operation of the prototype self-produced by the research group, in terms of stability of the device during high altitude flight and quality of georadar measurements.</p> <p>The total distance covered by georadar transects with ground-based measurements was about 6 km. distributed at altitudes between 2800 m and 3100 m above sea level.</p> <p>The data processing phase (carried out in June) made it possible to estimate along the investigated</p>							

¹ data as at 31 September

transects the seasonal snow thickness, the average thickness of which varied between 3 m and 4 m. The geophysical data were calibrated by point measurements of thickness, following the use of graduated probe. A second processing phase allowed the estimation of electromagnetic wave velocity values to derive through semi-empirical correlations the estimate of seasonal snow density.

Finally, it should be noted that the experimental acquisition and processing activities made it possible to codify a standard georadar survey protocol and related data calibration for characterization activities with non-invasive methods of snow cover.

Partner/Research teams: POLITO

Objective 2 – Monitoring

Task 1 – The stations of Bussoleno (Susa valley), Cannona (Orba valley) and Nivolet (Valsavarenche) have measured also in winter to continuously provide data of the water balance data.

Figure 1 – Nivolet weather station

Some monitoring of snow water equivalent has been done in the mentioned different areas of Piemonte and Valle d'Aosta, to test the innovative Time Domain Reflectometry (TDR) sensor which allows to get hundreds sparse measurements in a day. It is very important due to the extreme space variability of snow in the windy mountain environment.

Figure 2 –Nivolet station data: water level, EC and Temperature for both stream and spring.

Figure 3 –Snow melting, water balance description.

Figure 4 –Nivolet station data: soil moisture at 40cm depth.

Partner/Research teams: UNITO, POLITO

Task 2 - The infrastructure of the snow-meteorological monitoring station at the LTER Istituto Mosso site (Mosso Station) has been completed. An innovative sensor for monitoring the optical properties of snow has been installed and is in the process of data acquisition. In addition, work continued on technical requirements for the development of systems for quantifying precipitation/solids accumulation and estimating snow cover area from digital images, as well as sampling for the study of dissolved organic carbon content in surface water at the LTER Istituto Mosso site.

Partner/Research teams: UNITO

Objective 3 – Data Analysis and Forecasting

Task 1 – Development of machine learning tools which will be useful in the data analyses and forecasting activities of the next six-months period. The DAUIN Polito team and Links are developing a system to forecast river discharges using open data rainfall data provided by UniTO.

Partner/Research teams: LINKS, UNITO, POLITO

Objective 4 – Formation

Task 1 – Contributed to organize the training course FAO-Mountain Partnership 'Understanding the water challenges', in Collaboration with Italian Ministry of Foreign Affairs

Partner/Research teams: UNITO

Output and results:

- A paper about the use of cheap electrical conductivity measurements in mountain streams is published in open discussion in the website of the European Geophysical Union (Gentile et al., 2023).
- A poster about the interaction between monitoring sites and regional water authorities has been presented in Bonn in September 2023 and it will be soon published in the Tereno-Ozcar site (the network of monitored catchments in Germany and France).

Deviations (if applicable):

None

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

- A laboratory instrument for quality of water and soil has been purchased, together with a sonic anemometer for energy and evapotranspiration fluxes.
- An automatic salt solution provider, installed in Olen Valley at 2000 m asl beginning of September. It is very useful for the measurement of discharge in mountain streams, as evidenced by stakeholder meetings. Monterosa 2000 helped in the installation, being interested in ecological flow evaluation.

Figure 5 –Example of data extrapolated from the autosalt Olen Monterosa2000 station.

- Cosmic rays for both soil moisture and SWE measurements in Nivolet, Bussoleno, and Cannona sites.
- Soil moisture down to 2 m depth and three springs discharge measurements showed that the drought of 2022 is not yet recovered.

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

To continue installing instruments in the field, where it is possible to work: at the mountain is very short and it is necessary to define very precisely the different phases. Many activities are at more than 2500 m asl altitude. Many monitoring sites are already available and provide data automatically on the internet. The design of databases, digital twins and machine learning is on the way.

1.2.2 Research Module 2

Research Module n.2	Start month: 1				End month: 36			
Title: Integrated management of energy production and use								
Location in Mezzogiorno: N								
RM Leader	POLITO				Prof. Alfonso Capozzoli			
Partners involved	POLITO	UNITO	LINKS	UNIVDA				
Type of action:	Industrial Research							
Effort in person/months²:	14.08	0.34	6.76	0.09				
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):								
<p>The primary objective of the Research Module 2 is the conceptualization, development, and deployment of a co-simulation architecture to deeply study and analyze the integrated management of energy and water resources within renewable energy communities located in mountain areas. The proposed architecture was designed to easily operate models from various software platforms, each characterized by different temporal resolutions. The goal is to create an effective and robust tool for generating digital twins of renewable energy communities. This tool was conceived to support both the design stage of renewable energy communities and the optimization during operation of energy and water management, along with the integration of data analytics services to support the decisions of various stakeholders.</p> <p>Two main goals have been achieved during the reporting period:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) Enhancing the co-simulation architecture's capabilities to model the thermal behavior and dynamics of buildings within an energy community. ii) Efficiently integrating large-scale water reservoir models specifically designed for a case study aligning with the primary objectives of the NODES project. 								
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):								
<p>Objective 1: Enhancement of the co-simulation architecture for integrated management of energy and water resources in Renewable Energy Communities.</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">Task 1 – Design of the co-simulation architecture</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">Partner/Research Team 1: POLITO</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">Task 2 - Development and integration of a scalable process to build and deploy building energy performance models in a renewable energy community.</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">Partner/Research Team 1: POLITO</p>								

² data as at 31 September

Task 3 - Development and integration of a water multi-reservoir model for the co-simulation platform at daily /hourly scale

Partner/Research Team 1: POLITO

Objective 2: Development of a case study in Orco Valley by means of the co-simulation architecture.

Task 1 - Development of the Orco Valley Reservoirs network and evaluation of the water need for hydro-potable service.

Partner/Research Team 1: POLITO

Task 2 – Simulation of thermal behavior and energy demand of a renewable energy community: the case of Frassinetto municipality

Partner/Research Team 1: POLITO

Output and results:

Co-simulation Architecture (Objective 1 – Task 1).

Task 1 was aimed at the development and finalization of the proposed digital twin model, based on a co-simulation architecture for the integrated management of energy and water resources in Renewable Energy Communities. The co-simulation architecture was conceived for providing to digital twin designers and project stakeholders a comprehensive tool to easily interconnect heterogeneous models in a plug-and-play fashion with the aim to simulate integrated Renewable Energy Communities scenarios and manage energy and water resources during operation. The infrastructure leverages a multi-model view where the designer can choose among several interchangeable versions of the same simulated model, selecting from different engines (i.e., general purpose programming languages, software simulators, hardware simulators) depending on the required spatiotemporal scalability. This vision ensures the ability to simulate the fast-to-slow temporal evolution of a Renewable Energy Community scenario in a unique co-simulation infrastructure, easing the potential to scale the scenario under analysis by choosing the right combination of models in a distributed infrastructure. The infrastructure also provides the flexibility to develop innovative component models following the appropriate interfaces for data exchange, unlocking simulation capabilities for large-scale scenarios. Finally, the infrastructure offers the possibility of integrating real-world data coming from smart meters, applications and services to assess their functionalities within a digital twin approach. The overall framework of the infrastructure is reported in Figure 1, and it consists of three main vertical layers: I) the Data Source Layer, ii) the Co-simulation Layer, and iii) the Application Layer.

Figure 1 - Co-simulation Infrastructure.

The **Data Source Layer** contains the sources of information needed to describe a Renewable Energy Communities scenario, offering standard interfaces to access, query, and retrieve data from other layers of the infrastructure. It includes several database modules, and in particular:

- i) the GIS data sources to provide georeferenced data for the models of the co-simulation environments under specific scenarios (e.g. Census Data, Cadastral Maps, Digital Elevation Models, or Weather Data), ii) the Models data sources to provide basic elements for model definition, such as Building Archetypes & Data and Energy Networks (e.g., district heating, power network), Markets Data and Technologies Data of various energy systems, and iii) the Third-party sources to support the integration of additional third-party data sources.

The **Co-simulation Layer** is the core of the Hybrid Multi-Model Co-simulation Infrastructure. It sets up the co-simulation environment retrieving all the required information from the Application Layer. It is composed of three main horizontal layers, namely i) the Middleware Layer, ii) the Software Simulation Layer, and iii) the Hardware Simulation Layer.

The Middleware Layer is the central component of the Co-simulation Layer that provides the communication between the *soft real-time co-simulation* of the Software Simulation Layer and *hard real-time simulation environments* of the Hardware Simulation Layer exploiting a near real-time approach. It enables this communication by exploiting *VILLASframework*, a toolset for local and geographically distributed real-time co-simulations.

The Software Simulation Layer exploits a pure software co-simulation framework based upon Mosaik, a Python-based framework originally designed to co-simulate Smart Grid scenarios, but with the potential to be extended to cope with different energy domains. Its main core is the *COE Mosaik* that handles the initialization, the data exchange management, and the time regulation and synchronization of simulators and their model instances. During the

initialization phase, the *COE Mosaik* passes to all interconnected simulators their parameters (e.g. the number of model instances, time step duration, start date, end date) and model instances input/output relationships with other simulators' model instances. This important task is managed through the Scenario API that offers a common setup procedure for setting the scenario. Moreover, *COE Mosaik* manages the time regulation and synchronization of both Time-based and Event-based Simulators. Time-based Simulators evolve their model instances with a constant time stepped evolution. Vice versa, Event-based Simulators wait for specific asynchronous events to trigger their model instances' internal state changes and then forward their outputs to other simulators as events.

The data exchange management instead is achieved by exploiting the COE Interfaces that allow forwarding the initialization information, the time regulation and synchronization commands, and the model instances inputs/outputs to each interconnected simulator. Moreover, the COE Interfaces allow the distribution of simulators and their models on different computer clusters, enhancing their vertical and horizontal scalability. Finally, these interfaces could enable the inter-connection of Third-party Simulator to prevent Intellectual Property Right issues by exploiting the Simulator API. Thus, third-party companies can plug in their own models in a wider scenario without sharing their engines.

Mosaik offers two main COE Interfaces by design: i) the GPPL Interfaces that allows the interconnection of models designed with common programming languages (i.e. Python, C++, Java) to exploit their simulation libraries (e.g. pandapower, pandapipes), and ii) the Socket Interfaces that permits to interconnect distributed simulators via TCP or UDP protocol.

Mosaik has been extended by integrating an FMI Interface for FMI standard that permits the coupling of the models even if they are based on different DSPL and their simulation software (e.g. Modelica, EnergyPlus). The Software Simulation Layer employs a soft real-time regulation and synchronization that executes all models considering a common wall-clock time evolution synchronized with the Hardware Simulation Layer.

The Hardware Simulation Layer allows the interconnection of commercial Digital Real-Time Simulators (e.g. OPAL-RT or RTDS Technologies) to the co-simulation infrastructure. This layer can run specific models of components that require a hard real-time execution (e.g. power grid, electric vehicle charging system). Moreover, it allows Hardware-In-the-Loop (HIL) and Power Hardware-In-the-Loop (PHIL) to test and validate a real device in a protected virtual environment, avoiding huge deployment costs and the associated risk of deploying the component in a real-world environment. The DRTS exploits the common digital real-time capabilities of self-regulating the time evolution with small time step durations of around tens of microseconds. It offers by design different DRTS Interfaces to communicate with external entities.

The Application Layer manages the modules describing and composing a complex Smart Grid scenario into a co-simulation environment by selecting the proper models and interconnecting them together in a user-friendly and plug- and-play fashion.

The Model Catalogue acts as a library that collects all models from already deployed scenarios. Moreover, it gathers information on the configuration setup of each model, such as its time step duration, initial conditions, required inputs, provided outputs, and available data flows with other models. The Model Catalogue offers users the possibility

of extending the collection with new models by choosing one of the different possible simulation environments (i.e. simulation software, GPPL, and DRTS) with the proper co-simulation configuration required to interconnect the model to the Co-simulation Layer.

The Scenario Design module supports the user definition of a scenario for developing an innovative Smart Grid system by offering a comprehensive automated tool to interconnect models contained in the Model Catalogue in a plug-and-play fashion. This module offers a standard YAML configuration template to set up the scenario by exploiting a grey-box modelling approach with minimum effort and cost. By exploiting each model configuration and setup information that resides in the Model Catalogue, the YAML template guides the platform user in designing the scenario preventing the manual configuration and interconnection of models, which can be error prone.

Finally, the Scenario Builder oversees compiling the resulting scenario from the Scenario Design module and communicates its configuration to the Co-simulation Layer, which will instantiate and configure each individual model to concretely execute the co-simulation environment. The Scenario Builder will also validate the proposed scenario by exploiting simulator-specific knowledge (e.g., model configuration and setup information) from the Model Catalogue. This will enable the Scenario Builder to identify suitable interconnections, as well as to detect possible inconsistencies in the defined scenario with respect to typical input/output relationships captured by the model configuration and setup information. Moreover, the Scenario Builder will set up each individual simulator software, and DRTS for their physical interconnections and network communication to the Co-simulation Layer. The Application Layer also includes i) the Grafana Dashboard to present co-simulation results by retrieving information from the Scenario/Simulation Database in the Middleware Layer, and ii) the GIS Maps module instead exploits the georeferenced information from the Data Source Layer and present them into maps to better describe co-simulation results in a spatial scale.

Energy and Thermal Modelling (Objective 1 – Task 2).

EnergyPlus was selected as software to model energy demand and thermal dynamics of buildings within a REC. To this purpose, a scalable process was conceptualized and developed to automatically build detailed energy performance models of buildings. As shown in Figure 2, the process leverages GIS data to extract spatial distribution of buildings within a community. This data are employed to develop high-fidelity engineering models based on EnergyPlus software. These models also consider shadings from surrounding buildings.

Figure 2 – Framework of the process employed to build detailed models of building within a REC

In addition, a standardized methodology was adopted to define the thermophysical features of building envelopes on a large scale. The most common building constructions were examined using the Italian standard UNI/TR 15522:2014. The most representative building constructions of the case study were subsequently modelled in the EnergyPlus environment, generating three main building envelope archetypes that can be easily associated with the construction period:

- Construction archetype for pre-1950 buildings (stone masonry, concrete floors and timber roofs)
- Construction archetypes for buildings 1950-2000 (brick masonry, hollow black slabs and lightly insulated timber roofs)
- Construction archetype for post-2000 buildings (insulated masonry, insulated floor and insulated roof)

The co-simulation architecture can associate a specific building envelope archetype to each individual building in the scenario, depending on the building energy scenario generation strategy (i.e., year of construction, energy upgrading intervention, etc.). The developed methodology allows a representative energy scenario to be generated efficiently and quickly, without compromising a detailed characterization of the buildings' thermal behavior.

Water Modelling (Objective 1 – Task 3).

The software tool identified for the water reservoir modelling is *Generalized Multi-Reservoir Analyses using Probabilistic Streamflow Forecasts (GRAPS)*, in which reservoirs and users across the basin are defined using a node-link representation. Unlike existing reservoir modeling software, GRAPS can handle probabilistic streamflow forecasts represented as ensembles for performing multi-reservoir prognostic water allocation and evaluate the reliability of forecast-based allocation with observed streamflow.

Figure 3 - GRAPS flowchart.

As depicted in Figure 3, GRAPS offers a useful Python GUI to design the multi-reservoir model as a network of water components. The water components are highlighted in the example model legenda. The GRAPS GUI allows for the initialization of the file required by the GRAPS EXECUTABLE, the solver of the multi-reservoir model written in Fortran90. Moreover, the GRAPS GUI can execute the GRAPS EXECUTABLE and retrieve the output file for visualization purposes. As a consequence, the type of execution of GRAPS EXECUTABLE is a One Shot Execution as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - Stepping of GRAPS model.

To achieve the interconnection of GRAPS EXECUTABLE with the co-simulation architecture the One Shot Execution solver was transformed into a Time Stepped Execution solver, capable of producing output from input received each time step as depicted in Figure 4. The stepping of GRAPS EXECUTABLE was achieved with a flexible GRAPS Interface designed in Python that is capable of exploiting the co-simulation infrastructure i) to receive Inflow data as input by the co-simulation scenario, ii) set properly the input file required by GRAPS EXECUTABLE to run a single time step, iii)

calculate the multi-reservoir model solution by executing the GRAPS EXECUTABLE, iv) retrieve the output file containing the multi-reservoir model solution, v) send to the co-simulation scenario the water system balance of the multi-reservoir model. Moreover, the GRAPS Interface deals with the co-simulation API to receive management commands for the data exchange, time synchronization, and regulation. A high-level description of the GRAPS Interface is depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - GRAPS co-simulation interface.

To test the GRAPS Interface, a simple scenario was proposed where the Inflow data is read from the former inflow input file of the original GRAPS EXECUTABLE by the CSV Reader simulator. This simulator is a Python simulator capable of reading a CSV file and sending one of the values at each time step. These values are fed via the co-simulation infrastructure to the GRAPS model as shown in Figure 6. The water system balance as output of the GRAPS Interface instead is redirected via the co-simulation infrastructure to the HDF5 Collector, a Python simulator that can retrieve each time step water system balance state and save it into a Water System DB to store the results of the GRAPS EXECUTABLE.

Figure 6 – First water reservoir co-simulation environment.

The Braxil Example scenario contained in the repository of GRAPS have been used for validation purposes. Firstly, GRAPS EXECUTABLE has been executed in a One Shot Execution to retrieve the result of the standalone simulator. Then, the co-simulation infrastructure have been run in the configuration of Figure 6 to retrieve the co-simulated

simulator result. Finally, the result of the simple co-simulation scenarios have been compared. This experiment demonstrated the capability of the co-simulated GRAPS Interface to reproduce the same result of the standalone GRAPS EXECUTABLE.

Thermal modelling of Frassinetto Municipality (Objective 2 – Task 1).

This task was aimed at the implementation of the modelling process of energy demand of the buildings in Frassinetto Municipality to execute and test the co-simulation environment as proposed in (Objective 1 – Task 2). This modelling process requires the following steps:

1. Collection of GIS data of the buildings of the municipality, which includes:
 - a. Building gross surface coordinates for each building within the municipality.
 - b. Coordinates of the surfaces of surrounding buildings for each building within the municipality.
2. Assignment of the pre-defined envelope archetypes to each building
3. Extraction of fmu from EnergyPlus models for each building within the municipality.
4. Simulation of the thermal behavior and energy demand of each building for a period of the heating season with the following assumptions:
 - a. Heating is provided to the buildings to maintain a fixed setpoint of 20 °C.
 - b. Buildings are occupied according to a pre-defined occupancy schedule.
 - c. Window to wall ratio was set constant at 0.2

Water modelling of Orco Valley (Objective 2 – Task 2).

This task was aimed at the implementation of the GRAPS GUI (see Figure 7) to execute a co-simulation environment as proposed in (Objective 1 – Task 3) of the Valle Orco. This modelling process requires the following steps:

1. Thoroughly analyzing the system's structure, with a specific focus on interconnections and the hydraulic system.
2. Determining the necessary inputs, which includes:
 - a. Supply side characterization:
 - Establishing the physical parameters for each reservoir, such as storage limits and operational parameters.
 - Estimating coefficients for the Elevation-Storage Relationship and Area-Storage Relationship for each reservoir.
 - Estimating evaporation rates for each reservoir.
 - b. User-side characterization:
 - Examining the technical and operational characteristics of existing hydroelectric power plants.
 - Profiling and characterizing a representative user with municipal water requirements, particularly related to a new aqueduct project in the area.

Figure 7 - Part of the GRAPS water reservoir model of Valle Orco.

Publications (see Table 4)

- Rando Mazzarino P., Macii A., Bottaccioli L., Patti E., A Multi-Agent Framework for Smart Grid Simulations: Strategies for power-to-heat flexibility management in residential context. In: Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks, Elsevier. DOI: 10.1016/j.segan.2023.101072.
- Solinas F. M., Macii A., Patti E., Bottaccioli L., An Online Reinforcement Learning Approach for HVAC Control. In: Expert Systems with Applications, Elsevier. DOI: 10.1016/j.eswa.2023.121749

Deviations (if applicable):

The definition of design and planning scenarios with the aim of exploring options aimed to optimize the use of energy and water resources was postponed in order to focus the research effort on the simulation capabilities of the proposed architecture.

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling reserach activities:

None

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

The objectives for the next reporting period deals with the further advancement in the capabilities of the proposed co-simulation architecture, and in particular:

- Enhancement of the process for modelling building energy demand and thermal behavior to handle more detailed input information from different sources (e.g. form Energy Performance Certificates data base)
- Introduce a more accurate and larger description of the building envelope, with a higher number of

archetypes.

- Integration of models of various generators such as gas boilers and heat pumps along with storage technologies.
- Definition and simulation of different scenarios for the Frassinetto municipality aimed at showing the impact on energy performance of a potential renewable energy community of different configurations of technologies and management strategies
- Implementation and of a run-off model that takes climatic data (i.e, average temperature, precipitation) as input and provides accurate surface runoff as output. The objective is to carry out a hydrological analysis of the study area using GRASS GIS and subsequently determine surface runoff through a model implemented in R environment.

Figure 8 - Proposed co-simulation model for runoff.

- Definition and integration of different modules of a complex co-simulation scenario as described in Figure 9 by integrating: i) a Weather simulator, capable of retrieving the temperature, humidity, solar irradiance, and rainfall measurements from real-time third-party services; ii) the runoff model that receive the Weather simulator output to calculate the inflow of different basin of the water system of interest; iii) the GRAPS Interface simulator that receive the inflow as input to calculate the water system balance, and, finally, iv) the HDF5 Collector simulator that is capable of collecting the water system balance input to store them in a Water System DB.

1.2.3 Research Module 3

Research Module n.3	Start month: 1				End month: 36			
Title: Risk-resilient Energy and Water Infrastructures								
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y								
RM Leader	POLITO				Prof. Daniele Peila			
Partners involved	POLITO	UNITO	LINKS	FMS	UNIBAS			
Type of action:	Industrial Research							
Effort in person/months³:	12.97	0.81	4.48	2.70				
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):								
<p>Water adduction, water collected in reservoirs and energy transmission network in mountain environments are typically subject to multiple natural hazards such as landslides, accelerated soil erosion, earthquakes, snow avalanches, glacial collapse, river floods, which can induce critical interruption and/or reduced efficiency in the services provided by the utility companies.</p> <p>Through digitalization, infrastructure systems can become more resilient, as well as provide rapid, accurate asset conditions assessments to support decision-making and adaptation. Droughts as well are challenging energy and water supply utilities. Digitalization can help in a better knowledge of the effects of these hazards and the management of their effects also taking into account the climate change effect.</p>								
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):								
Objective 1 - Avalanches								
Task 1 - Study of areas subjects to avalanches and development of automatic procedures to compute:								
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) the avalanche dynamic and its impact on the energetic infrastructures; 2) the definition of detachment points; 3) the hazard conditions of energetic infrastructures. 								
<p>In the first year, has been developed a correlation between the static variables (geological) and the dynamic variables (mainly linked with the meteorological conditions) to be used for the definition of instability indexes.</p> <p>Application of these indexes in a GIS mapping to assess hazard conditions with special reference to energetic infrastructure networks. This work is in progress.</p> <p>The dynamic of the avalanches has been studied using the open access code Avaframe based on a DTM.</p> <p>A specific back-analysis of an event occurred in Valsarvarance (AO) in 08/01/2018 that damaged a high tension pylon has been carried out.</p>								

³ data as at 31 September

A study of the detachment point related with the slope dip has been carried out with reference to relevant case histories in Piedmont and Aosta Valley (data Base of ARPA Piemonte and Comando Truppe Alpine-Servizio Meteomont) .

Partner/Research teams: POLITO, UNITO, FMS

Task 2 – Historical analysis of the energy distribution networks that were impacted both in Aosta Valley and in Piedmont.

Many case histories have been reported and analysed with the goal to understand the interaction between the avalanche flow and the electricity pylons. The evaluation of the fragility curves of the high-tension pylons and single poles when impacted by an avalanche has been developed.

The data for the avalanche maps and the position of the energetic infrastructures has been extracted from the databases and they will be used in the Digital Twin model.

Partner/Research teams: POLITO, UNITO, FMS

Task 3 Glacier

A database of ice avalanches in Aosta Valley and on the Alps (including information on the collapsed volume and angle of reach) has been developed.

The mapping of all the water intake and hydroelectric plans of CVA on Aosta Valley has been collected with the goal to develop a methodology for risk assessment related with the impact of ice collapses on these infrastructures.

The development of the detailed maps of the potential risk induced by glacial collapse in Aosta Valley is in progress.

Objective 2 - Slope stability

Task 1 - Literature review of the impact of the climate change on the slope stability in Alpine environment.

Definition of the static variables (geological and structural) and weather conditions to be used as indicators of an instability. Application of the study to the Monte Rosa area.

Partner/Research teams: POLITO, UNITO

Task 2 – Development of the tools for the generation of digital hazard maps able to consider as a key parameter the Climate Change impact (i.e. the change in precipitations and temperature). This activity is in progress

Partner/Research teams: POLITO, UNITO

Task 3 - Design model and procedures of the devices that can be used to protect energetic infrastructures with specific reference to wire drapery mesh and rockfall protection embankment.

A wire drapery mesh design scheme has been developed. The procedure and the model have been published on an international paper.

Physical models in scale of embankments have been constructed and tested with the goal to assess the collapse condition. A report has been developed.

The tests have shown that the use of optical fibres due to the construction procedures are not very effective and they will not be used for further development of the research.

Geophysical tests have been carried out on a rockfall embankments in Aosta valley with the goal to define the quality of these structures. A report has been developed.

Partner/Research teams: POLITO, UNITO

Objective 3 - Stability of reservoirs with earth dams

Task 1 – Definition of the procedure for testing integrated geophysical surveying on earth embankments to be used for water storages in high mountains in Aosta Valley.

Execution of tests on some sites on Aosta Valley

The Interpretation of the results of the test will lead to the definition of a standard procedure. Activity in progress.

A permanent monitoring set up has been installed to check its feasibility during a long period. This activity is in progress.

Development of a digital mapping on Open GIS platform of the activities of characterization and of the monitoring devices of the water reservoir

Partner/Research teams: POLITO

Output and results:

Journal paper

- M. Marchelli, A. Pol, D. Peila, F. Gabrieli (2023) Towards a Hybrid Design Approach of Anchored Drapery Systems, *Geosciences* 2023, 13(5), 147
- Marchelli M., Peila D., Giacomini A. (2023) Rockfall in open pit mines: management of the pit geometry and protection measure design, *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences*, 170, 105551
- Marchelli M., Coltrinari G., Degan G. A., Peila D. (2023) Toward a procedure to manage safety on construction sites of rockfall protective measures, *Safety Science* 168, 106307

Conference paper

- Bovet Eloïse, De Biagi Valerio, Durand Nathalie, Debernardi Andrea, Roveyaz Simone (2023) A multilevel framework for the management of energy infrastructures involved by avalanches, *ISSW 2023, Bend (Oregon)*

Data sets or guidelines

- DTM data of avalanches and energy networks in Aosta Valley (with Fondazione Montagna Sicura) to be used in the Digital Twin.

- Data for the definition of the geometry of the avalanches and the damages suffered by electricity networks (in cooperation with ARPA - Dipartimento Rischi Naturali e Ambientali Struttura Semplice Monitoraggi e Studi Geologici).
- Extraction of the layers "Tralicci linee elettriche alta tensione" of BDTRE. Crossing these data with the position of areas subjected to avalanches and natural hazards zones.
- Procedure for geophysical testing of rockfall embankments.
- Procedure for the assessment of the scale embankments.

Field test network

- Installation of a permanent geophysical monitoring set up on a reservoir earth embankment.

Participation to international conferences

- ISSW2023

MSc Thesis

- 1 MSc thesis at Politecnico di Torino (titled "Effetti delle valanghe di neve sulle infrastrutture energetiche") Laurea Magistrale in Ingegneria per l'Ambiente e il Territorio,
- 2 MSc thesis at Università di Torino Corso di laurea in Scienze e Tecnologie dei sistemi forestali

General public activity & seminars

Presentation of a poster at Politecnico di Torino event "Climate action" (13/10/2023) Title 'Climate Change Impacts on Infrastructures in Alpine Areas'.

Event organized by 2i3T (incubatore di UniTo) with a presentation on "Ghiaccio e neve in un clima che cambia: il progetto PNRR - NODES - Montagna digitale e sostenibile".

Seminar au UNITO on "Alpine hydrogeology: The critical role of groundwater in sourcing the headwaters of the world" by prof. Masaki Hayashi della University of Calgary, Canada.

Deviations (if applicable):

None

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling reserach activities:

Assistance and material supply for small-scale rockfall embankment experimentation for 3 days.

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

Development of the activities in progress as indicated in the activity description

1.2.2 Research Module 4

Research Module n.4	Start month: 1	End month: 36					
Title: Smart Energy and Water Distribution Systems							
Location in Mezzogiorno: N							
RM Leader	POLITO			Prof. Davide Poggi			
Partners involved	POLITO	FMS					
Type of action:	Industrial Research						
Effort in person/months⁴:	16.61	0					
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):							
<p>The increasing water demand for hydropower and the impact of climate change on the availability of water requires a dramatic re-thinking how to keep the lights (and the taps) on, while both are making the best use of new energy (and water) sources and keeping infrastructure costs down. Instead of only extending and reinforcing physical infrastructure, which is extremely costly and disruptive to local communities, new management policies and systems are needed to arrive at decisions that narrow the discrepancies between stakeholders (i.e. energy producers, drinking water suppliers and irrigation consortia). To support these decision-making approaches, it is necessary to implement a better knowledge of the systems that use the water resource at the basin scale. Complementary, IT solutions must be developed, adding communication, sensors, and automation, allowing distribution-system operators to actively manage the varying generation and demand. This combination of solutions is what is commonly referred to as a smart grid. Digitalization of the energy and water distribution networks will prospectively increase the security of supply, improve the quality of service, and better respond to demand from customers.</p>							
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):							
<p>Objective1 - Digital models of the transmission and distribution networks and innovative smart-grid solutions.</p> <p>Task 1 - Mapping of major transmission and distribution infrastructure.</p> <p>Activities focused on the collection of geo-referenced data to complete the GIS mapping of the basin chosen as a case study for the implementation of the Digital Twin: the Orco Valley.</p> <p>Task 2 – Investigation of the available data network at the basin scale.</p> <p>In collaboration with RM1, all ARPA monitoring stations located in the Orco Valley area were mapped and geo-referenced. Historical data were stored up to the time present in the dataset described in Table 6.</p> <p>Identification of the water intake and return network along the basin. Construction of a logical interconnection network between each intake and its downstream return works required for task 2 of the objective 2.</p> <p>Partner/Research Team: POLITO</p>							

⁴ data as at 31 September

Objective2 - Innovative solutions for increasing and better managing the water storage capacity and energy production.

Task 1 - Implementation of a multi-reservoir model of the Orco valley.

A basin-scale multi-reservoir model for simulation and optimization of water resource management was developed in collaboration with RM2 (Objective1, Task3). The case study chosen is the Orco Valley. The main activities were the description and to the conceptual representation of the water infrastructure network in the Orco Valley, as well as the identification of the main input data for the planned model such as: geometric parameters of the dams in the area, estimation of the reservoir curves, evaporation parameters and yields of the installed production plants.

Partner/Research Team: POLITO

Task 2 - Water availability.

Calculation of the Orco Valley hydrographic network and estimation of flow duration curves at each node by Regionalization method. The activities involved the use of GIS tools for watershed analysis, identification of the hydrographic network, and sub-basins related to each node in the network. Additional applications developed in R, MatLAB, and Python allowed the identification of the network of intakes and returns present in the sub-basins as well as the calculation of the new ecological runoff (replacing the previous DMV) for each of the nodes in the reticulum. Integration of duration curves with flow intake/return and ecological runoff data to estimate water volume available for hydropower scope.

Partner/Research Team: POLITO

Task 3 – Energy potential

Preliminary activities on estimating the hydropower potential at each node of the Orco Valley hydrological network based on data from Task 2.

Extrapolation of solar irradiance data over the Orco Valley basin at 100m resolution from the PVGIS-SARAH2 dataset for further investigation about the photovoltaic potential.

Partner/Research Team: POLITO

Output and results:

- Updated version of the Orco Valley GIS map that include:
 - ARPA monitoring networks
 - Water intake/returns including the logical interconnection network
 - Energy transport infrastructure
 - Maps of landslide areas
 - Maps of buildings and their heights above ground level
 - Digitalized layout of the new Orco Valley aqueduct
- Contributed to populating the flagship dataset with the monitoring network data and GIS data described

above.

- Estimation of water availability with duration curves calculated on about 4700 nodes of the hydrographic network with a resolution of 100m per cell.
- Orco valley multi-reservoir model to be tested. In a preliminary stage, the flow rate estimated from the duration curves calculated by the Regionalization method (Objective2 – Task2) will be used as inflow of the model.
- Maps of monthly average solar irradiance.

Deviations (if applicable):

None

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

None

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

- Finish the activities related to the estimation of hydropower potential, including the results in the GIS map.
- Test the multi-reservoir model on different simulation scenarios

Key Indicators for Research activities and Flagship Projects:

The KPIs achieved by the flagship during the reporting period are summarized in the table below.

		Flagship Target	Flagship progress for the reporting period
Outcome	Number of Pilot Line / Demonstrators / Prototypes	1	0
	Number of publications	29	14
	Number of registered IPR (patents, utility models, trademarks, industrial designs)	1	0
Output	Number of professor and researcher involved	14	33
	Personnel effort dedicated to Research and Innovation and Flagship Project (person/month in three years)	130	72.96 ⁵

2. IMPACT

According to the EUSALP strategy, digitalization through connectivity and digital services can be a way to address the critical challenges of mountain areas, such as depopulation, brain drain, physical barriers, accessibility to welfare and economic growth (www.alpine-region.eu). Based on this line of reasoning, this flagship project considers the use of digital technologies to improve the performance of enterprises located in mountain areas by reducing or resolving the critical issues identified in the EUSALP strategy. In addition, digital technologies can be a way to combat the brain drain by attracting and retaining skilled workers in mountain regions. Digitalization becomes important to an efficient and sustainable use of water and energy resources, to reduce travel and to make it easier living in mountain areas for people working for companies wherever located on the territory of the ecosystem (mountain and plain).

To date, the project's progress has focused on the area of academic research and has generated a good number of scientific publications with a significant impact in the scientific field. Also, some monitoring innovative sensors have been tested at different altitudes, sometime helped by mountain industry (e.g.: Monterosa2000). In the coming period, an increased impact can be expected in other fields such as industrial production (start of activities of the companies selected in the cascading calls).

⁵ data as at 31 September

3. INDUSTRY PARTICIPATION AND INNOVATIONS (prototypes, clinical trials, Testing activities etc)

The flagship project will generate significant industrial impact in the NODES ecosystem through the digital transformation of some key activities in mountain areas. Digital transformation is brought forward through different transmission channels. By providing innovative digital solutions for firms in the realm of smart working and digital compliance, it contributes to digital transformation of the economic fabric of the territory. New organizational forms leading to inflows of high-skilled workers from different part of the NODES ecosystem to the mountain areas generate the knowledge spillovers and new start-up. Demand for new services from delocalized working activities as well as the definition of new digital solutions for firms and citizens stimulates the creation of new innovative and digitally oriented firms. In the context of green development, innovation activities can not only promote the efficiency of resource allocation and enhance the core competitiveness but can also drive the high-quality socio-economic development of the region. During the reporting period, discussions continued with the main companies and stakeholders in the NODES area. The project promoted with companies the opportunities related to the cascading calls published by the NODES project. Activities are at a preliminary stage, the companies involved in the cascading calls will start their activities in the next few months.

A meeting between the coordinator of module 1 and Hortus was done at the Hortus headquarters in Gallarate the 24th Oct. in order to discuss in presence with the German producer of GNSS antennas for snow water equivalent measurement to be installed in three sites.

FOLLOW-UP OF RECOMMENDATIONS AND COMMENTS FROM PREVIOUS REVIEW(S) (IF APPLICABLE)

Not applicable yet.

4. OPEN SCIENCE PRACTISES AND UPDATE OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (IF APPLICABLE)

Not applicable yet.

5. RESULTS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART

Not applicable yet.

ANNEXES

A) LIST OF DELIVERABLES

D. No	Name	RM No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Status	Comments
D1	Flagship Work Programme	/		R	PU	M2		30/11/2022	Submitted	Description of the flagship activities
D2	Technical Call fiche	/		OTHER	PU	M2		30/11/2022	Accepted	Calls published by M2, Hiring completed
D3	Geodatabase structure	All		OTHER	SEN	M12		31/10/2023	Submitted	Geodatabase structure for digital twin implementation
D4	Progress Report Flagship Projects SUMMER	All		R	PU	M12		31/10/2023	Pending	Second progress report Flagship project
D5	First dataset delivery	All		DATA	PU	M12		31/10/2023	Submitted	First delivery of the integrated dataset from modules 1-4

Table 1: Deliverables

B) LIST OF MILESTONES

Milestone No	Milestone Name	RM No	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Achieved	Comments
1	Launch of research	all		Deliverables D1-D2	M6		M6	YES	
2	First Dataset Delivery	all		Deliverables D3-D4-D5	M12		M12	YES	

Table 2: Milestones

C) LIST OF CRITICAL RISKS.

Risk No	Did you apply risk mitigation measures?	Did your risk materialize?	Comments
1	NO	NO	No partner-related risk issues have been identified so far
2	NO	NO	No planning problem have been indentified so far.
3	NO	NO	Initial results from research activities have not produced any critical issues concerning changes of priorities in research projects.
4	NO	NO	The solutions developed are at a preliminary stage, but no problems with scalability or lower than expected results have been reported.
5	YES	Partially	Data availability is crucial. To mitigate this risk, appropriate data harvesting mechanisms are set in place to track progress of availability of data.
6	NO	NO	The solutions developed and the results are at a preliminary stage but initial results have already been published in scientific journals and presented at conferences.

Table 3: Risks

D) PROJECT PATHWAY TO IMPACT: RESULTS

Not applicable yet

E) PUBLICATIONS

Type of publication	Peer-review	Type of PID (repository)	PID of deposited publication	Link to publication (if no PID of publication)	Title of the publication (for book chapters: title of chapter not of book)	PID of publisher version of record	ISSN/eISSN (if book insert ISBN)	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Number	Publisher	Month/Year of publication	PID of book (if book chapter)	Book title (if book chapter)	Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication	License type	RM
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.159195		A stochastic cellular automaton model to describe the evolution of the snow-covered area across a high-elevation mountain catchment			K.J. Painter, A. Gentile, S. Ferraris	Science of The Total Environment	857	ELSEVIER	10/2022			YES	CC BY	RM1

Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences13050147		Towards a Hybrid Design Approach of Anchored Drapery Systems			M. Marchelli, A. Pol, D. Peila, F. Gabrieli	Geosciences 2023	13(5)	MDPI	03/2023			YES	CC BY	RM3
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.162777		Hydrological, thermal and chemical influence of an intact rock glacier discharge on mountain stream water			F. Bearzot, N. Colombo, E. Cremonese, U. Morra di Cella, E. Drigo, M. Caschetto, S. Basiricò, G.B. Crosta, P. Frattini, M. Freppaz, P. Pogliotti, F. Salerno, A. Brunier, M. Rossini	Science of The Total Environment	876	ELSEVIER	03/2023			NO	Other	RM1
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2022-921		Towards a conceptualization of the hydrological processes behind changes of young water fraction with elevation: a focus on mountainous alpine catchments			A. Gentile, D. Canone, N. Ceperley, D. Gisolo, M. Previati, G. Zuecco, B. Schaeffli, S. Ferraris	Hydrology and Earth System Sciences	27	EGU	05/2023			YES	CC BY	RM1

Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3275435		A Comparative Evaluation of Deep Learning Techniques for Photovoltaic Panel Detection From Aerial Images			E. Arnaudo, G. Blanco, F. Dominici	IEEE Access	11	IEEE	05/2023			YES	CC BY	RM2
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segan.2023.101072		A Multi-Agent Framework for Smart Grid Simulations: Strategies for power-to-heat flexibility management in residential context.			Rando Mazzarino P., Macii A., Bottaccioli L., Patti E.,	Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks, Elsevier		ELSEVIER	05/2023			YES	CC BY	RM2
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/acdb88		Unprecedented snow-drought conditions in the Italian Alps during the early 2020s			N. Colombo, N. Guyennon, M. Valt, F. Salerno, D. Godone, P. Cianfarra, M. Freppaz, M. Maugeri, V. Manara, F. Acquaotta, A. B. Petrangeli, E. Romano	Environmental research letters	18	IOPScience	06/2023			YES	CC BY	RM1

Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrmms.2023.105551		Rockfall in open pit mines: management of the pit geometry and protection measures design			M. Marchelli, D. Peila, A.Giacomini	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ROCK MECHANICS AND MINING SCIENCES	170	Elsevier	07/2023			YES	CC BY	RM3
Publication in conference proceeding	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS52108.2023.10281933		LAND COVER SEGMENTATION WITH SPARSE ANNOTATIONS FROM SENTINEL-2 IMAGERY			M. Galatola, E. Arnaudo, L. Barco, C. Rossi, F. Dominici	Proceedings of the IEEE International Symposium on Geoscience and Remote Sensing		IEEE	07/2023			YES	CC BY	RM1
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2023.1234976		Editorial: Hydrological and chemical effects of a changing cryosphere on mountain freshwaters			Nicola Colombo, Stefano Brighenti, Thomas Wagner, Sudeep Thakuri, Franco Salerno	Frontiers in Earth Sciences		Frontiers	07/2023			YES	CC BY	RM1
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2023.106307		Towards a procedure to manage safety on construction sites of rockfall protective measures			M. Marchelli, G. Coltrinari, G.A. Degan, D. Peila	Safety Science	168	Elsevier	09/2023			YES	CC BY	RM3

Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2023.121749		An Online Reinforcement Learning Approach for HVAC Control.			Solinas F.M, Macii A., Patti E., Bottaccioli L.,	Expert Systems with Applications	ELSEVIER	09/2023			YES	CC BY NC ND	RM2
Pre-print	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2023-1797		Technical Note: two-component Electrical Conductivity-based hydrograph separation employing an EXPONENTIAL mixing model (EXPECT) provides reliable high temporal resolution young water fraction estimates in three small Swiss catchments			A. Gentile, J. von Freyberg, D. Gisolo, D. Canone, S. Ferraris	Hydrology and Earth System Sciences	EGU	09/2023			YES	CC BY	RM1
Publication in conference proceedings	YES	pURL	https://arc.lib.montana.edu/snow-science/item.php?id=2910		A MULTILEVEL FRAMEWORK FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF ENERGY INFRASTRUCTURES INVOLVED BY AVALANCHES			E. Bovet, V. De Biagi, N. Durand, A. Debernardi, M. Marchelli, S. Roveyaz	International Snow Science Workshop Proceedings 2023, Bend, Oregon	ISSW	10/2023			YES	CC BY	RM3

Table 4: Publications

F) DATASETS

The first integrated dataset of the four research modules was delivered. The dataset represents the general repository structure and contains an initial collection of data. The repository will continue to be populated throughout the duration of the project in order to ensure that the desired results are achieved in terms of the Digital Twin platform.

Short Name:	FS-SUMMER
Description of datasets:	Integrated dataset of the 4 RMs
Data origin:	31/10/2023
Data type:	Numeric, geospatial, time-dependant
Data Formats:	Multiple: .csv, .shp, .gtif, .xlsx, .pdf
Useful for whom:	Digital Twin platform
If data is needed to validate conclusions of a scientific publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make it available	[N/A]
Findability (Type of PID, PID of deposited dataset):	https://github.com/FS-SUMMER/Dataset.git
Accessibility:	<i>Partially open, access with request</i>
Interoperability:	
Reusability:	GNU General Public License v3.0 GNU General Public License v3.0
Open	YES

Table 5: Data sets

G) INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS (IPRs)

Not applicable yet

H) OTHER RESULTS

Not applicable yet

I) IMPACT in terms of TRLS, SDGs, KSOs

Not applicable yet

Technology readiness level of the project	
At project' start: [an item.] Current status:[an item.]	<p>Expected by Project 'end:</p> <p>[TRL1- Basic principles observed]</p> <p>[TRL2- Technology concept validated]</p> <p>[TRL3 - Experimental proof of concept]</p> <p>[TRL4 - Technology validated in lab]</p> <p>[TRL5- Technology validated in relevant environment]</p> <p>[TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in relevant environment]</p> <p>[TRL7 - System prototype demonstration in operational environment]</p> <p>[TRL8- System complete and qualified]</p> <p>[TRL9 - Actual system proven in operational environment]</p> <p>[Not applicable]</p>

Table 6: TRLs

Is your project likely to deliver results relevant for the following Sustainable Development Goals?	
Climate neutrality (SDG 13)	[Fully relevant]
Clean Water and Sanitation (SDG 6)	[Fully relevant]
Life Below Water (SDG 14)	[Not relevant]
Life on Land (SDG 15)	[Partially relevant]
No Poverty	[Partially relevant]
Zero Hunger	[Not relevant]
Good Health and Well-being	[Not relevant]
Gender Equality	[Not relevant]
Decent Work and Economic Growth (SDG 8)	[Partially relevant]

Affordable and Clean Energy (SDG 7)	[Fully relevant]
Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure (SDG 9)	[Fully relevant]
Reduced Inequality	[Partially relevant]
Sustainable Cities and Communities (SDG 11)	[Fully relevant]
Responsible Consumption and Production (SDG 12)	[Partially relevant]
Quality Education	[Not relevant]
Peace and Justice Strong Institutions	[Not relevant]
International cooperation	[Not relevant]
Please explain your choice	<p>The SUMMER flagship project aims to accompany energy and water management into the digital era, showing how smart technology can boost the integrated management of water and energy systems (SDG 6) fostering the sustainable production and distribution of energy (SDG7). Digital technologies, combined with the power of 'big data' and AI-based analytics, drive unprecedented innovation in how energy and water utilities and companies manage these vital resources (SDG 8 / SDG 9), contributing to protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems (SDG15) and combatting climate change (SDG 13).</p> <p>Working with local stakeholders and raising awareness among policymakers and industry in the tangible benefits for a transition towards a Circular Economy helps NODES' cities and communities to implement integrated policies and plans towards resource efficiency, mitigation and adaptation to climate change (SDG 11).</p>

Table 7: SDGs